

Effect of Sugars on CMC of Aqueous Solution of Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

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The effect of glucose, fructose and sucrose on the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of a cationic surfactant, *i.e.* cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) has been studied conductometrically at 35°. It has been observed that on addition of varying concentration of D-glucose and sucrose (0.05-0.3 M) the CMC of CTAB increases. The first CMC of CTAB in pure water is found to be 9.0×10^{-4} M at 35° by this method. However, in presence of varying concentration of D-fructose the CMC decreases initially and then increases.

A close review of literature indicates that the effect of additives has been studied on the CMC of surfactants by many workers¹⁻¹⁰. Effect of co-solvents on thermodynamics of aggregation of surfactants in aqueous solutions has also been examined^{11,12}. Blandamer *et al.*¹³ have found that by addition of glucose, fructose and arabinose to the micellar catalysed reaction of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene with hydroxide ions, the first order rate constant increases, indicating an enhancement of the catalytic action of CTAB. But they have mentioned that attempts to measure the effect of sugar on the CMC of CTAB proved unsuccessful. In fact there is hardly any study on the effect of sugar on the CMC of surfactants and this enthuse us to take up this problem. Recently we have communicated¹⁴ our findings on the change of CMC of an anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaLS) by addition of sugars.

Experimental

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (B.D.H., England) was purified by the method of Duynstee and Grunwald¹⁵. D-glucose, D-fructose and sucrose were of E.M. reagent grade and used without further purification. All the solutions were prepared in triple-distilled water.

In order to prepare good number of solutions of varying concentration of CTAB (of the order of 10^{-4} M) maintaining a fixed concentration of sugar in it, different volumes of CTAB and sugar solutions of appropriate concentrations were mixed and diluted with triple-distilled water. The specific conductance of these solutions were measured at 35° putting the conductivity cell in a thermostat using Systronics 304 digital direct reading conductivity meter. Then graphs were plotted with [CTAB] vs specific conductance. The CMC value was found out from the break point on the graph. CMC of CTAB in the absence and presence of a series of

sugar concentrations were determined similarly and different sugars tried.

Results and Discussion

The first CMC of CTAB in pure water at 35° was found to be 9.0×10^{-4} M and increased gradually by the addition of different quantities of glucose and sucrose, but when fructose was added the CMC decreased and then increased slowly (Table 1). The concentration of sugars have been varied from 0.05 to 0.3 M and the experimental CMC values are given

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF CMC OF CTAB IN AQUEOUS SUGAR SOLUTIONS OF VARYING CONCENTRATION AT 35°

Additive	CMC $\times 10^4$ M	ΔG_m^0 kcal mol ⁻¹
Nil	9.0	7.37
D-Glucose		
0.10	9.2	7.36
0.15	9.4	7.345
0.20	9.6	7.33
0.25	10.0	7.30
0.30	12.0	7.19
D-Fructose		
0.05	6.5	7.56
0.10	7.0	7.52
0.20	8.0	7.44
0.25	8.4	7.41
0.30	8.6	7.40
Sucrose		
0.05	10.4	7.28
0.10	12.0	7.19
0.15	12.8	7.15
0.20	13.8	7.09
0.30	15.6	7.04

in Fig. 1, which shows the molar CMC of CTAB at 35° as a function of molarity of the organic additive, the sugars. In case of NaLS, addition of all these sugars have shown rise in the CMC values and it is in the order, D-fructose > sucrose > D-glucose¹⁴. But in case of CTAB, some differences were noted. By addition of D-fructose, instead of

Fig. 1. CMC's for CTAB in aqueous sugar solutions at 35°: ●, sucrose; ○, glucose; □, fructose.

increase of CMC of CTAB it decreased, whereas sucrose and D-glucose have maintained the same trend as in case of NaLS. The latter sugars at 0.3 M concentration have raised the CMC of NaLS about 3 and 5 times whereas the corresponding values with CTAB are about 1.33 and 1.50 times, respectively.

The effects of various sugars on the CMC are displayed in a somewhat different manner in Fig. 2, i.e. as $-RT \ln X_0$ vs mole-fraction of sugars, where X_0 represents the CMC in mole-fraction units. For calculating the mole-fractions the volume of solutes have not been taken into consideration. Blandamer *et al.*¹⁸ have observed a dramatic rate enhancement by the effect of added fructose in the reaction

Fig. 2. Stability of CTAB micelles in aqueous sugar solutions at 35°: □, fructose; ○, glucose; ●, sucrose.

mentioned earlier. But by addition of fructose the CMC decreases in our case. However, they have carried on their kinetic studies in more diluted solution of sugars (*ca.* 10 times) and concentrated solution of CTAB (*ca.* 10 times) in comparison to our work.

Emerson *et al.*¹ have observed that addition of sucrose to aqueous solution of a cationic surfactant increases the CMC but they have not focussed their attention in particular on sucrose so far their discussion is concerned. In general, they have suggested the increase of CMC is due to the breaking of micelles and penetration of additives. They have also explained it taking thermodynamic parameters into account. There are also additives which are non-penetrating in nature but still influence the aggregation of surfactants.

The values of ΔG_m^0 have been computed from $-RT \ln X_0$ and have been given in Table 1. It is the standard free energy of transfer of a monomer from aqueous phase to an aggregate which already contains the number of monomers at the CMC, i.e. to a micelle of average size \bar{m} . In case of D-fructose at 35°, ΔG_m^0 values are more negative and, hence, more stable is the micelle, under the experimental condition in comparison to D-glucose and fructose.

The effect of additives on CMC can be discussed in term of the change in water structure. The formation of the so-called iceberg structure around the hydrocarbon chains of surfactant molecules bring about a loss of entropy at their dissolution. For charged micelles thermodynamic parameters are complex, since they represent a composite of hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions. Sugars are water-structure makers and due to the presence of more number of hydroxy groups sucrose is a better structure-maker than glucose and fructose. In case of CTAB micelle the head groups will be strongly hydrated in the presence of sugars. Sugars being dipolar in character, it may so happen, that some of the water molecules around the positive head group may be replaced by sugar molecules as a result of which the electrostatic interaction between the head group and counter-ion decreases. Under such situation, the CMC of CTAB increases when sugar concentration is increased. An increase in the CMC may be partly due to the increase in the number of free counter-ions for adsorption of sugar molecules in the Stern layer of the surfactant micelle.

Gratzer and Beaven⁴ have marked the CMC decrease to small extent by addition of sucrose in case of a nonionic surfactant where it can be explained only on the basis of hydrophobic interactions since electrostatic interactions are not involved. In the present study, CMC of CTAB decreases by the addition of fructose only. It seems, all the factors controlling the CMC including concentration of CTAB and its cationic nature and the concentration of fructose and its structure making character are

ideal for which the CMC decreases where the structure making character has predominated.

The CMC increase observed in case of sucrose is more than that of glucose as sucrose is a better structure-maker than glucose for having more number of hydroxy groups and its bulky structure. The system of CTAB, sugar and water is extremely complex. Hence, to offer explanation for the interactions of these hydrophilic sugars becomes difficult and further study in this line is in progress.

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